

KPI Assurance in Deterministic Optically Interconnected Cloud/Edge Infrastructures

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Abstract: *Several industrial use cases require the deployment of computing resources over distributed computational facilities. However, quasi-deterministic communications are a must in this scenario, arising the need for performance assurance.*

Keywords: *Optical network design, control, management, and security; Inter- and hyper-scale intra-DC networks; Internet of Things (IoT) aware systems and applications.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The rise of novel industrial applications, such as industry 4.0/5.0 use cases (UC), entail the control and monitoring of distributed Internet of Things (IoT)-based assets. To these purposes, the deployment of specialized functions in the form of control/management applications is needed [1]. Generally speaking, the deployment of these applications requires the usage of computational resources (hosted at servers). Given the computational resource requirements (CPUs, memory, storage) of the applications, these may be deployed at the server of choice, either directly (bare metal deployment) or exploiting virtualization techniques (e.g., Virtual Machines (VMs), containers). However, aside from computational resources, the deployment of these applications also entails the communication between the remote assets (e.g., automated guided vehicles, robots' arms, etc.) and the computational resources in which they have been deployed. Such remote control implies that communication latencies and data losses must be minimized, having a tight control over the experienced values. Therefore, a timely communication between remote end-points is required [2]. This not necessarily imposes low latencies, but determinism in them is a must so as to guarantee that data exchanges arrive at the desired time.

For this reason, the usage of distributed local computational resources (distributed edge sites) is preferred, due to the proximity to the IoT-based (client) end-points. However, to ensure that deterministic Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are met, specialized network fabrics are employed to interconnect the distributed edge sites. Much work is being devoted to provide deterministic capabilities to classic electronic-switched Ethernet networks (typically network fabrics in edge segments), with the aim to extend said capabilities to the rest of infrastructures involved in the remote communication with the computational resources. However, because edge sites typically have limited resources (for scalability reasons and to maintain agility), applications may lack the necessary computational resources for deployment.

In such situation, the usage of remote cloud infrastructures (i.e., datacenters (DCs)) may be beneficial. However, due to the longer network paths, time-based metrics (e.g., latency and jitter) budgets must be carefully evaluated, potentially reducing the number of applications that can be deployed at the cloud. Nevertheless, there are cases with less stringent, but still bounded, KPIs that may allow for the deployment of applications at centralized remote cloud infrastructures, for instance, by splitting the applications functionalities into several parts, one being deployed at close edge sites due to requiring an agile communication with the end-points, and another, with more relaxed communication requirements, exploiting the cloud infrastructures. In such scenario, end-to-end (E2E) connections are required to be established between cloud and edge resources. In order to satisfy the KPIs, conscious efforts in the development of technologies for both intra- and inter-DC networking are a must, in what has been labeled as deterministic cloud infrastructures [3]. In this context, inter-DC and edge-to-DC communication present a challenge, as deterministic guarantees must be ensured across long distances and multiple network segments. Transparent optical networks emerge as a promising solution due to their inherently low latency and jitter-free nature [4], enabling the development of distributed deterministic cloud/edge infrastructures. However, this is only feasible if KPI assurance is enforced when establishing network connectivity. Additionally, it is crucial to ensure that network resource allocation does not degrade the performance of existing traffic flows. Therefore, a KPI-aware provisioning phase is essential to prevent performance issues in deployed services.

II. KPI-AWARE RESOURCE PROVISIONING FOR INDUSTRIAL UCS

Fig. 1 depicts the situation in which an industrial end client, decides to deploy some of the control applications of its internal operations into the distributed cloud/edge infrastructure. In this regard, applications are modelled by having two sub-applications, one required to be deployed at the local edge and another that may be deployed at a remote cloud infrastructure. A metropolitan distributed edge infrastructure is considered, in which several edge sites are distributed within a confined geographical area. Each of the edge sites can be modelled as having an aggregated capacity of computational resources, to be exploited by local users, which connect to the edge sites by means of access networks (not depicted in the figure). Then, the several edge sites are interconnected by means of a metropolitan area network, so as to provide connectivity between the distributed sites as well as towards other network segments/domains. Each of the edge

sites has a node that acts as gateway towards the metro network. We assume that an electronic-based network with deterministic capabilities is employed, due to both cost reasons and capacity requirements. Several metropolitan regions are then interconnected by means of a transparent Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) optical network which allows for the access to remote cloud infrastructures. In such scenario, the deployment entails two aspects: 1) Deployment of the control application at computational resources; and 2) Interconnection of the local edge resource and the cloud. This last step requires both the provisioning of lightpaths within the WDM segment and the connections inside the electronic network. The intra-DC networking aspect is left out from this work. Let us assume that the connections to support the deployed application are characterized by a requested bit-rate plus a maximum allowed latency and jitter. The connections also state a KPI satisfaction degree in the form of a percentage, which indicates the probability of fulfillment of the stated KPI [5]. For example, a value of 90% would mean that, statistically, the KPIs must be respected in a 90% of the connection lifetime. However, due to the stochastic nature of some of the network components (e.g., traffic queues/buffers), KPI assurance becomes challenging. Focusing on the latency aspect, the contributors to the E2E value are multiple: 1) the propagation delay of the physical links; 2) the switching time at optical nodes; 3) the queueing and service time at electronic nodes. The same reasoning applies to the jitter.

Given this stochastic nature, it becomes essential to have tools in place to guarantee the KPIs during application deployment, which, in essence, translates to finding network routes that satisfy the stated maximum latencies and jitters. In practice, this is a fairly complex and costly process, which requires the deployment of several probes as well as a monitoring framework capable of flow-level KPI measurement. Other options may exploit the usage of machine learning techniques of digital twin frameworks so as to predict the achievable performance given a concrete resource layout. As an alternative, in [6] we presented a statistical model that allows to estimate the latency and jitter of deterministic network services across optically interconnected client domains. However, it does not suffice that the provisioning of the applications at the deterministic cloud/edge considers the achievable KPIs of the candidate routes, but it becomes imperative that the impact of the new service onto the existing ones is carefully analyzed. For instance, it may happen that, while the selected network resources, given the current E2E network state yield to acceptable KPIs for the application being deployed, the selected layout would increase the latency or jitter of the flows sharing network resources with it. Fig. 1 depicts an example in which two flows are established between a remote cloud infrastructure and local edge resources. The black solid line represents the latency threshold for flow 1, considering that flow 2 is later established following the stated path. This would yield to an unacceptable degradation of the KPIs. Hence, it becomes mandatory to evaluate the impact of the candidate deployment onto the previously provisioned applications and associated connectivity. To this end, we properly extend the estimation engine developed in [6]. As such, the provisioning becomes as follows: 1) find within the local edge the resource that can host sub-application 1 and the cloud site that can host sub-application 2; 2) use the estimation engine to find KPI-compliant (latency and jitter) candidate paths between selected end-points; 3) for the explored paths, check if its selection would yield to degradations of previous deployments, employing the developed statistical model. If no, the paths are selected, reserving the bandwidth across the entire path, exploiting lightpath grooming at the optical segment. If the selection would yield to a degradation, the next candidate path is explored. However, it may happen that, depending on the network conditions, all the candidate paths are not feasible as they would impact in any case some established flows. In this situation, the deployment would be blocked. Nevertheless, no affection to live applications/flows would happen. This signals an interesting trade-off, in which KPI degradation or blocking due to not having suitable network path candidates arises. Next section sheds light in this aspect.

Fig. 1. Application deployment at optically interconnected deterministic cloud/edge infrastructures.

III. EVALUATION AND DISCUSSION

We showcase the benefits of KPI-awareness deterministic deployment while assuring the KPIs of the already deployed applications at the distributed cloud/edge infrastructure (hereafter check approach). To this end, we employ the topology of Fig. 1, in which all link distances are expressed in kms. We consider a propagation delay of the network links of 4.67 μ s/km, a switching time of optical nodes equal to 1 ms and queues of size 20 packets per port and priority at the electronic nodes. We consider three priorities, each one capable of handling independent traffic flows through their dedicated

queues. Next, we consider that all network interfaces work at 10 Gb/s, with WDM links at the optical network having 40 wavelengths per link. Finally, we consider that the cloud infrastructure has an equivalent aggregated capacity in terms of computational resources equal to 100 CPUs, 40 GB of memory and 40 TB of storage, while each node at the distributed edge has an equivalent capacity of 10 CPUs, 4 GB of memory and 4 TB of storage. Several requests for application deployment arrive following exponentially distributed holding and inter arrival times (HT, IAT), with load defined as HT/IAT. Each part of the application (sub-applications 1 and 2) is characterized by requiring between 1-2 CPUs, 12-256 MB of memory and 100-200 GB of storage. As for the connection between them, a bit-rate between 500-1000 Mb/s is assumed, stating a KPI set in terms of latency, jitter and satisfaction degree equal to 10 ms, 0.5 ms and 90%, respectively.

Considering all these characteristics, we employ two allocation strategies: 1) KPI-aware path computation with no check, used as benchmark of the proposed approach; and 2) KPI-aware path computation with check. The two strategies leverage on the aforementioned engine. First, we analyze the ratio of applications that suffered degradations in their connections' KPIs due to coexisting traffic flows for the case of no check. Fig. 2 (left) depicts the obtained results, considering 10^4 random requests per data point, with the left y axis depicting the ratio of degraded applications, that is, applications in which traffic flows have experienced some KPI degradation during their duration, in the no check case and the right y axis the blocking due to no suitable network paths found in the check case. It can be seen how, if no check during the deployment of applications is done, there is a share that experience KPIs degradations during their lifetime, up to around 0,5% in the worst case. This stems from the fact that new deployed applications would have their connections, if allocated, sharing resources with already deployed ones, increasing the traffic at the electronic queues. As a consequence, larger queueing times are experienced, increasing the connections latencies and jitters beyond their stated KPIs, causing the degradation. To counteract such effect, the check strategy is employed. In such a case, this phenomenon is not observed, since the check avoids any kind of degradation by design when jointly selecting the computational and network resources to deploy the application. Nevertheless, it may increase the blocking of new requests due to the lack of suitable network paths. However, it can be appreciated that this blocking is below the share of degraded applications, and only experienced at higher loads. To further analyze the benefits of this strategy, Fig. 2 (middle) depicts on the one hand the average degradation period of affected applications, computed as the portion of its lifetime in which some of its connections' KPIs are degraded and, on the other hand, the average KPI stretch, computed as the average ratio of the degraded KPI and the nominal requested value. As an example, a KPI stretch of 1,01 would mean that in average, the KPI has been degraded by a 1%. For this last metric, we focus on the latency of network connections. It can be appreciated how the degradation period can be significantly large (up to 90%), resulting in a KPI degradation between 0,17-1,2%. This clearly indicates that degradations can occur, increasing their severity the higher the network load, thus having a mechanism that avoids such situations is a must. Nevertheless, this checking process has as a consequence an increased complexity, which translates to higher provisioning times. Fig. 2 (right) shows the execution time of both strategies for three working points. The checking strategy results in more than thrice the execution time. However, its added benefits compensate for the increased operational cost, which is still compatible with typical deployment times.

Fig. 2. Ratio of degraded applications and blocking due to no suitable network paths (left), average degradation period and KPI stretch (center), provisioning time (right).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Cloud infrastructures may be used to deploy control applications of industrial UCs with deterministic requirements. However, distributed deterministic cloud/edge sites require of a fine assessment of the KPIs, specially the network related ones. We analyzed the impact of KPI degradations in latency bounded application deployments and showcased how KPI estimation tools contribute to avoid said degradations, with minimal impact on the number of accepted applications.

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